

SOME OBSERVATIONS ON THE FACTORS THAT LED TO THE
FORMATION OF ALLIANCES AMONG THE
CENTRAL ASIAN NOMADS

Shavkat Safaraliyevich Amonturdiyev,
Independent student of Termiz State University

sh.amonturdiyev@mail.ru

Abstract. In the article, the author spoke about the issues of statehood, political alliances and the factors of their emergence, the reasons for their disintegration, as well as the theoretical and practical research conducted in this direction and some conclusions based on them in the early nomadic peoples of Central Asia.

Keywords: *Nomadic peoples of Central Asia, Sakas, Massagets, political alliances, political, economic, social, and demographic factors, archaeological research on nomadic tribes*

Access. In the formation of the first statehood in the territory of Uzbekistan, along with settled peoples, nomadic peoples have their place. Tribes such as Sak and Massaget are among the oldest ethnic groups in the process of formation of the Uzbek people. The fact that the nomadic tribes living between Amudarya and Syrdarya founded the great ancient states of Kang and Kushon shows that they have an important place in the ethnogenesis of the Uzbek people and the history of statehood. In the creation of the history of Uzbek statehood, special attention should be paid to the role of nomadic peoples in the process of formation of statehood. Although the statehood of nomadic tribes of Central Asia cannot be equated with the statehood of settled peoples, the study of the history of their cultural and political processes shows how this issue was.

The main part. Studies show that cattle-herding tribes who created the Tozabogyob culture of ancient Khorezm were also engaged in primitive agriculture in the low parts of ancient water basins. Semi-basement dwellings, hand-made and decorated with various geometric patterns, typical of the Tozabogyob culture, are similar to ceramics from the desert zones of Kazakhstan and Siberia. Based on this, S.P. Tolstov considered the Tozabogabo people to be the descendants of the Andronova tribes. In the archeological sources, there is no evidence of sharp conflicts between the inhabitants of the two zones from the monuments of these periods [1].

In Greek sources, the people who lived in the desert zones of Eurasia were called Scythians. Pliny expressed the following opinion about this: "the Persians call them Sakas after the tribes living near them" [2]. In ancient Iranian sources, Shak (Sak) and Scythian ethnic names are found [3]. Ancient Iranians called the tribes living in the desert zones of Central Asia with such ethnic names. Iranian historian V. Abayev considers the "races" mentioned in the "Yasht" part of "Avesta" to be the Sakas of Central Asia, and the "races with fast horses" and "danoy" are the Sakas who lived on the banks of the Syrdarya [4].

Since the first settlers of Central Asia were mainly engaged in animal husbandry, according to the economy of their settlement process, they are traditionally classified as follows:

1. Nomadic tribes living in areas without clear boundaries (not demarcated).
2. Nomads living in clearly defined (bounded, fixed) areas.
3. Nomads who live next to settled oases or in lands suitable for farming.

The settlement of the third group of tribes from the above was relatively faster. However, in the 6th century BC, the Central Asian nomads formed a military alliance of tribes or political associations to protect their lands from the attacks of other tribes. The factors for the formation of these alliances are different. Including:

A) Natural factors

1. Climatic changes are one of them, the arrival of cold or dry nature caused the migration of tribes.

2. Intensification of permanent military conflicts for favorable geographical areas as a result of the vagaries of nature.

3. Infectious diseases, various epidemics, etc.

B) Economic factors

1. First of all, nomadic herders have a strong desire for places that are convenient for their livestock - serum meadows.

2. Along with pastures, permanent water sources (springs, lakes, river valleys, etc.) are necessary for nomadic pastoralists.

3. As a result of the favorable climate, the number of livestock, which is considered the main wealth, has increased and the desire to own it (the process of transformation from collective property to private property and stratification) has increased.

4. As a result of property stratification, classes emerged in society.

5. Constant maintenance of contacts with other tribes and settled peoples.

6. Interconnections are carried out through permanent roads with specific addresses.

7. The presence of natural reserves of the region (iron, etc.) in the settlements of the nomads helped them in mutual relations.

8. The constant existence of trade relations carried out through caravan routes can be explained as follows:

- As a result of the nomadic way of life, the shortage of some daily consumer products for internal needs and certain dependence on settled oases in this regard;

- In the economy of nomadic herders, livestock and livestock products form the basis of production, while a certain amount of manufactured products are exported to settled neighbors. The adoption of various new areas of production increased the volume of products for the market.

- Caravan trade serves as one of the means of permanent income.

C) Political factors

1. As a result of the increase in the population of the nomads, the demand for new land increased as usual.

2. Occupying convenient geographical and important strategic areas has become an urgent issue.

3. Tribes did not neglect defense and combat training to maintain their political influence.

4. Confederations were always formed to achieve a specific goal, and this was considered an extremely important factor for the future fate of the union.

5. The fact that the union of tribes in the nomadic peoples is not at the level of the statehood of the settled peoples is the long-term preservation of the clan system in them.

6. Unions in nomadic tribes had their political governance and had a special influence on the people's assembly.

7. Military chiefs or tribal rulers were elected by popular assembly, as in many other highly developed nomadic nations of the world.

8. In tribes and alliances, the rule gradually passed from generation to generation.

9. The ideas of the people's assembly and the mutual equality of the nomads testify to the existence of certain specific, defined laws and rules in them.

10. The influence of the military in society increased, and this was also caused by constant military campaigns. Military campaigns differed depending on the purpose:

- To protect their lands from the attacks of neighboring tribes (defense);
- To acquire new lands as a result of population growth (exploitation);
- Robbery or military campaigns carried out by military commanders to gain personal wealth;

G) Demographic factors

1. The increase in the population of nomadic tribes automatically increased the demand for new land.

2. The protection of the tribes' land is considered an urgent issue.

3. In contrast to settled peoples, migration processes have continued continuously and this has an important place among their demographic factors. The reasons for migration are also different:

- As a result of climate change;

- During the military conflict, weak tribes were pushed out of their lands or forced to move to other lands;

- Sometimes tribes changed their places of residence as a result of epidemics;

The variety and number of names of nomadic tribes in Central Asia are related to the formation and disintegration of political associations of nomads. Because when the tribe that joined the political union left it, they moved to other territories under a new name and formed new alliances.

Constant contact with the settled population and other nomadic tribes played an important role in the formation of political associations among Central Asian nomads. The political associations formed by the nomadic tribes of Central Asia were formed based on specific agreements and confederal rules. Their nomadic lifestyle caused this situation to develop slowly. The fact that the statehood of the nomadic tribes of ancient Central Asia was not at the same level as the statehood of the settled population was more related to the way of life of the tribes and the conditions of the union that arose. These alliances were created with the following conditions:

1. Tribes fought to preserve their freedom and independence in the alliance of tribes formed to protect themselves from the attacks of other tribes.

2. As a result of the increase in the population, the living areas of the tribes

become narrow, and alliances are formed with neighboring tribes to occupy new lands.

3. Alliances of tribes formed to loot or invade the lands of settled peoples and other tribes to get out of the crises caused by adverse weather conditions.

4. Nomadic tribes break their competing tribes in various fields (for example, for leadership or territories), etc.

The main reason for the defeat of Cyrus II of Iran by the Central Asian nomads is that the idea of freedom of the country is not a personal interest in the military alliance of tribes formed to protect their country.

Political associations of Central Asian nomads were formed to protect their lands from neighboring tribes or invasions in case of serious military danger. As vivid examples of this, we can point to the emergence of large political associations during the military campaigns of the Achaemenid kings Cyrus II and Darius I, as well as Alexander the Great. The killing of Cyrus, the defeat of Darius, the fact that the military pressure of Alexander the Great in Central Asia did not reach the land of the settlers, or the stopping of the invasion campaigns determine the enormous political and military influence of the confederations.

CONCLUSION. The factor that influenced the further duration of the union of tribes in the nomads is the confederative rules. In many cases, to achieve this specific goal, there was a violation of the terms of the contract, which was created based on certain conditions, besides, the alliances quickly disintegrated due to the above-mentioned factors. So, as a result of the increase in the population of the tribes, the demand for new land has constantly increased. To satisfy the need for new lands, the lands of neighboring tribes were taken over, the weak ones were forced out, and nomadic tribal unions were formed to defend their lands or organize large military campaigns.

REFERENCES.

1. Asqarov A. «O'zbekiston tarixi» (Eng qadimgi davrlardan eramizning V asrigacha). – Toshkent, 1994. 61-b.
2. «Древние авторы о Средней Азии». –Тошкент, 1940. — С. 126.
3. Дандамаев М.А. «Иран при первых Ахеменидах» . – М., 1963. –С. 262-269.
4. Абаев В.И. «Скифский быт и реформа Зороастра» . Аоч. XXIV. 1956, №1.

